

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION THROUGH THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF TECHNICAL FIELDS

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda texnikani o'qitish texnologiyasining ijobiy ta'siri yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *yelpigich metodi, Venn diagrammasi, texnikani o'qitish, pedagogik texnologiya.*

Abstract: This article describes the positive effects of teaching technology using new pedagogical technologies.

Key words: science method, Venn diagram, technique teaching, pedagogical technology.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещаются положительные эффекты технологии обучения технике с использованием новых педагогических технологий.

Ключевые слова: метод науки, диаграмма Венна, методика обучения, педагогическая технология.

Today, the content, goals and objectives, forms and methods of education are being improved. Such changes in our society require the use of modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process. In addition, the need to prepare young people for life requires us to introduce new technologies into the education system and their implementation [1].

The concept of educational technology is a science (or doctrine) that provides information about the organization of the educational process at the level of high qualification, art, lexically (eng. "an educational technologists"), meaning nose.

One of the first tasks of teachers is to mobilize all available resources for the proper organization of the educational process.

Changing the model of communication between teacher and student is one of the conditions of pedagogical technology.

In the USA in 1961 the journal "Pedagogical Technology" was published, in 1971 the Communications and Technology Association was established. 1971 Audiovisual Communication Statement magazines began to be

published. In 1964, the journal "Pedagogical Technology and Education Program" was published in England. In 1967, the National Council for Pedagogical Technique was established. In 1970, the journal Pedagogical Technology was published.

In Japan, in 1965, the "Council of the All Japan Center for Educational Technology" was established. The journals "Pedagogical Technology" and "Research of Pedagogical Technology" were published.

In 1973, the National Center for Educational Technologies was established in Hungary [2,3]. The development of society is created by the fact that each new generation inherits the legacy of the previous generation, enriches it and leaves it to the next generation. The term "pedagogy" originated in Ancient Greece (Greece) and is based on the word "teacher". In ancient Greece, a teacher was a slave who accompanied a student to school and served him in and out of the classroom. The Greek word "peidagog" ("paidi" - child, "gogos" - leader) means "leading child".

"Technology" is a scientific discipline that develops and improves methods for obtaining, processing and processing materials or semi-finished products. At the same time, the emergence of pedagogical technology is due to the fact that teaching is the same type of activity as other production activities. The term pedagogical technology has not yet been standardized, so it has many definitions. As an example, we give some definitions of pedagogical technology (PT).

PT is an algorithmic activity of teachers and students based on the construction of learning situations. (Palchevsky, Friedman)

PT is the systematic and consistent implementation of a pre-designed learning process. (V.P. Bospalko)

PT is the art of learning with a machine, or likening teaching to engineering. (G. Ilyin)

Software is a complex process that includes the analysis and planning, supply, evaluation and management of problem-solving activities, people and ideas of all learning equipment (Pedagogical Communications and Technology Association).

Given that there are many definitions of pedagogical technology, given that the term is not standardized, it is appropriate to refer to the definition given to it by the authoritative organization UNESCO.

Pedagogical technology is the creation, application and identification of the entire process of learning and learning, which sets itself the task of optimizing the forms of learning, taking into account technical and human resources and their interdependence, is a systematic view.

fan method

This method focuses on complex, interdisciplinary and often problematic topics. The essence of the method is that it explains all aspects of the topic

(for example, pros and cons, advantages and disadvantages, advantages and disadvantages, other qualities). For now, each of them is defined separately and discussed accordingly.

This interactive method allows students to successfully develop critical, analytical, clear, logical thinking, as well as the ability to express and defend their thoughts in writing and orally.

The fan method is aimed at organizing the active work of small groups, as well as each participant, as well as the entire group, in which certain aspects of a common topic are discussed.

The fan method can be used at different stages of the study of the subject:

at the beginning: free activation of students' knowledge;

in the process of studying the topic: deep understanding and understanding of its foundations;

at the final stage: regulation of the acquired knowledge.

Using this method, the following basic concepts on the topic will be studied:

concepts, perspectives, objects, events related to the topic;

advantage - superiority, privilege compared to something;

defect - imperfection, non-compliance with the rules, criteria;

virtue - positive qualities;

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In addition to the educational goal, the fan method allows you to perform the following educational tasks:

ability to work in a team, in a group;

problems, the ability to discuss situations from different points of view [5]

Fan analysis of gas laws

Boyle-Mario

T = constant
PV = constant

$$\frac{V_1}{T_1} = \frac{V_2}{T_2}$$

$$P_1 V_1 = P_2 V_2$$

Gale Lusac

P = constant

Charles

V = constant
P/T = constant

$$\frac{P_1}{T_1} = \frac{P_2}{T_2}$$

Ideal gas laws

VENN DIAGRAM:

This technology can be used at the lecture reflection stage. The purpose of the Venn Diagram technology is to enable students to think on the basis of the knowledge gained during the course, compare scientific and theoretical information, and find similarities and differences between various processes. Students reflect on what they learned in the lesson and how this information can be used in practice.

Students are given the opportunity to analyze, synthesize and generalize by comparing the common and different aspects of two or more questions that have different and common characteristics.

- Venn diagram:
- Used to compare, contrast, contrast and generalize aspects 2 and 3.
- Develops the skills of systematic observation, comparison, comparative analysis and synthesis [4].

RECOMMENDATIONS:

1. А. Каримов. «Своё будущее мы построим своими руками» «Ташкент». 1999 г.
2. Н.Н.Азизходжаева. Педагогические технологии и педагогическое мастерство. Ташкент 2006
3. Коканбаев И., Юлдашева М., Салимов О. «Образование и обучение в академических лицеях и профессиональных колледжах: проблемы и решения» Коканд-2008.
4. Н.Садриддинов, А.Рахимов. Основы преподавания физики. Ташкент. 2006 г.
5. В.Г.Разумовский. Развивать творческие способности учащихся. Ташкент. 1978 г

